

Possible Anti-Parkinsonian Compounds—Part VII Synthesis of Amidomethylation Products with N-Hydroxymethyl nicotinamide and Their Conversion into Quaternary ammonium iodides

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Six new amidomethylation products have been synthesized with the condensation of equimolar amounts of N-hydroxymethylnicotinamide and compounds containing active hydrogen atoms. These amidomethylation products thus prepared have been converted into the quaternary ammonium iodides with a view to evaluate their anti-parkinsonism-activity.

IN continuation of our previous work¹, some new pyridine derivatives have been synthesized. Pyridine derivatives have been reported to exhibit marked antiparkinsonism²⁻³, anticholinergic⁴ and antidepressant⁵ properties, in addition, quaternary ammonium salts of pyridine derivatives have been shown to increase the antiparkinsonism and anticholinergic activities because the quaternary ammonium salts avoid or minimize the side effects due to the stimulation of the central nervous system by the tertiary amines⁶. This led the authors to synthesize amidomethylation products with N-hydroxymethyl nicotinamide and their conversion into corresponding quaternary ammonium iodides with a view to testing their antiparkinsonism activity.

The synthesis was accomplished along the following route : (see Structure)

Experimental

N-Hydroxy methyl nicotinamide :

This was synthesized according to the method of Zhdanovic⁷.

Amidomethylation products with N-hydroxymethyl nicotinamide :

The amidomethylation was carried out by dissolving the reactive hydrogen compound (0.01M) in conc. H₂SO₄ (20-25 ml) and adding to it slowly under cooling N-hydroxymethyl nicotinamide (0.01M) and leaving the reaction mixture at room temperature for 48 hrs. The resultant mixture was then poured on crushed ice and the amidomethylation product thus precipitated, was washed with water to remove the sulphonated products. It was then dried and

R = phthalimido :
benzamido :
nicotinamido :
 β -naphthyl :
p-cresyl-.

recrystallised from ethanol. Various amidomethylation products thus obtained are listed in Table I.

POSSIBLE ANTI-PARKINSONIAN COMPOUNDS—PART VII

TABLE 1—AMIDOMETHYLATION PRODUCTS OF N-HYDROXY METHYL NICOTINAMIDE

Sl. No.	R	M.P.* °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Nitrogen	
					Calc.	Found
1.	Nicotinamido	250	75	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂	21.87	21.34
2.	Phthalimido	215	72	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₃	14.94	14.48
3.	Benzamido	185-6	71	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂	16.47	16.25
4.	3 : 5-Dibromo-salicylamido	240-1	71	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₃ Br ₂	11.18	10.86
5.	β -Naphthyl	115-6	68	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂	10.07	9.84
5.	<i>p</i> -Cresyl	120-1	65	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂	11.11	11.88

* Melting points are taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. All the compounds were recrystallised from ethanol.

Quaternary ammonium iodides of amidomethylation products :

Acetophenone (0.008M), iodine (0.007M) and amidomethylation products (0.008M) were mixed together and were refluxed on water bath for about 3-4 hrs and the resultant reaction mixture was allowed to cool. A solid mass was thus obtained and to it acetone (0.01M) was added; on cooling at 0°, crystals of quaternary ammonium iodides of amidomethylation products were obtained. It was filtered and washed with water and recrystallized from benzene. The quaternary ammonium iodides thus prepared are listed in Table 2.

Pharmacology :

The compound Nos. 1, 2, 3, of Table 1 and 2, 4 of Table 2 were screened for their anti parkinsonism activity in rats against Oxytremorine-induced tremors. None of the compounds were found to effect the tremor in rats up to 500 mg/kg i.p. dose. However, these compounds possessed central nervous system depressant activity. The compound no. 2 of Table 1 significantly increased the pentobarbitone sleeping time and had LD₅₀ 800 mg/kg.

TABLE 2—QUATERNARY AMMONIUM IODIDES OF AMIDOMETHYLATION PRODUCTS

Sl. No.	R	M.P.* °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Nitrogen	
					Calc.	Found
1.	Nicotinamido	120-1	50	C ₂₅ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₄ I ₂	7.48	7.16
2.	Phthalimido	90-1	55	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ N ₃ O ₄ I	7.96	7.44
3.	Benzamido	150-1	53	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₃ I	8.36	8.05
4.	3 : 5-Dibromo-salicylamido	107-8	53	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₃ IBr ₂	6.34	5.88
5.	β -Naphthyl	95-6	51	C ₂₅ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₃ I	5.34	5.59
6.	<i>p</i> -Cresyl	104-5	50	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₃ I	5.70	5.12

* Melting points are uncorrected; solvent used for the recrystallisation is benzene.

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